

THE IMPORTANCE OF CRITICAL THINKING IN WRITING COMPETENCY FOR ESL LEARNERS

Nazarova Gulbaxor Azimjon qizi,
USWLU, Associate professor, PhD

Tolipova Muhayyo Ahmad qizi.
USWLU, English teacher

Annotation

This article discusses the importance of improving writing skills among ESL learners in Uzbekistan, highlighting the critical role of teaching critical thinking as a means to enhance these skills. It emphasizes that effective writing goes beyond grammar and vocabulary and it requires organization, coherence, and the ability to construct logical arguments. The authors cite various scholars to support the argument that critical thinking is essential in language learning, especially in academic settings where students are often evaluated on their ability to analyze texts and express their ideas systematically. Besides, the article asserts that fostering critical thinking skills is vital for preparing Uzbek ESL learners for academic success and meeting the demands of the global educational landscape.

Key words: writing skills, critical thinking, English proficiency, essay, education, linguistic, peer reviews, texts, analytical skills, proverbs.

The improvement of writing skills among ESL learners in Uzbekistan is essential for their academic achievements. It is firstly a skill through which majority of ESL learners are assessed in tertiary education. Besides, due to the growing demand for English proficiency in higher education and professional fields, there is a dramatic need for students with the ability to deliver their ideas clearly. Nowadays, employers value graduate employees who can transfer their critical thinking to the workplace (Tapper, 2004). Critical thinking, defined as “skills or

abilities including selection, evaluation, analysis, reflection, questioning of certain information” (Tapper, 2004) plays a major role in enhancing writing competency. This article argues that teaching critical thinking is significant to improve the writing skills of ESL learners, thereby giving them a chance to meet academic standards of universities and excel in their studies.

Critical thinking has been comprehensively explored in the field of education, with a number of scholars putting an emphasize on its role in successful language learning. Language learning is no longer solely memorizing vocabulary and grammar rules. In order to foster successful communicators in a foreign language, which is the greatest purpose of teaching a language, deep comprehension, analysis of information effectively should be also taught by promoting critical thinking. In the context of ESL education, by means of critical thinking learners are encouraged to engage with texts more deeply, evaluate arguments, and express their points in a systematic and coherent way. In particular, effective teaching process of English cannot be imagined without integrating critical thinking skills as it is one of most typical cultural behaviors in English-speaking countries.

Writing competency includes not only good use of varied grammar structures and appropriate vocabulary, but also plenty of other skills including organization, coherence and the ability to construct arguments. At universities virtually all formal assignments are evaluated for both the language proficiency and and the clear explanation of presented ideas. Indeed, argument is considered as the primary expression of critical thinking in higher education (Andrews 1995, Scott 2000). I would absolutely agree with the statement mentioned by Bonnett (2001, pp.50-51) which says: “Your essay is your argument, everything else makes sense because of it”. Precisely, if an academic item of writing should be regarded as a good writing piece, the writer must be able to present an argument and prove it with strong and relevant supporting points by using critical thinking skills. Hence, integrating

critical thinking into this process enables learners to approach writing tasks methodically, thereby enhancing the overall quality of their work.

In Uzbekistan, it should be admitted that English language curriculum has experienced significant changes over the past decade, with a substantial emphasis on communicative competence. Consequently, the increasing number of English learners are able to use the language in linguistic and cultural contexts without much difficulties.

Nevertheless, when it comes to writing competency of ESL learners, there still exists a noticeable gap in incorporating critical thinking skills into writing instruction. For different reasons and in most cases, they have difficulty in analyzing texts and expressing their ideas critically. According to Biggs (1987,1994) and Ballard and Clanchy (1991), it can be seen that majority of Asian students avoid a critical approach to academic texts and they do not possess enough knowledge about what is involved in critical analysis. When it comes to reasons of this non-critical characteristics of Asian students, Andrews (2007) associates it to our “educational system based on rote-learning and their deference to teachers and scholars, where any critique can be construed as being impolite and disrespectful”. The reality of this case is embedded even in our proverbs which says: “Ustoz otangday ulug” (Your teacher is as respected as your father). As an Uzbek student who has studied for 12 years and graduated from a common public school in Uzbekistan, I cannot agree more that we have gained much information mostly by rote learning without giving much attention to analyze or questioning the relevance of it to our interests or future professions. As a result, it is making students unable to deal with complex writing tasks required in academic settings since majority of these tasks involves analyses and reflection – skills which do not form part of their education in their L1 (Ramanathan and Kaplan, 1996). There is another prime reason why Uzbek ESL learners often struggle with critical analysis and argumentation in their writing.

To successfully eliminate these challenges, first of all, educators must prioritize the integration of critical thinking into writing curricula. We can achieve it by creating assignments which encourage students to analyze texts, engage in debates, and develop their arguments systematically. Adding a wide range of genres to curriculum, such as opinion pieces, book reviews and reflective essays, can contribute a lot to increase critically analyzing obtained information before producing written assignments.

Another modification that should be inserted is in the sphere of assessment. Students should be wide aware that their writing will be marked not only for the content knowledge or the proficient language which is used in essays, but also for critical evaluation of the topic as well. If certain percentage of assessment of written assignments is devoted to critical thinking skills in this way, students also make an effort to integrate it in their writings to elevate their scores.

Effective teaching strategies are highly likely to promote critical thinking skills in academic contexts as well. These strategies includes collaborative learning, Socratic questioning, and the use of real-world scenarios to stimulate critical thinking. For instance, group discussions and peer reviews can foster a supportive environment where students learn to articulate their thoughts and critique others' work constructively. Real-world case studies can force learners to think of their own reactions in the given situations and make informed decisions.

Furthermore, introduction of simply asking questions on the topic can highly increase critical thinking. In our culture, majority of students hold back when asking questions or sometimes are not aware how to questioning the topic in writing assignments. They should be taught how to look at a certain issue from a wide range of viewpoints, such as learning its relevance or effect to environment, society, finance, culture, relationships, medicine, health and other spheres. They have to learn to question even their own arguments or beliefs as well by utilizing WH-questions such as “How do I know it?”, “Why do I believe it?”, “What examples

can I list to prove it?” (Andrews, 2000)

Additionally, educators should provide explicit instruction on the writing process, emphasizing the role of critical thinking at each stage. According to Mitchell et al.(2008), critical evaluation can be lacked in student’s works because of vague explanation and instruction of university tutors. Students are supposed to know what exactly is expected from them in their writings if want to obtain our expected outcomes at the end.

In conclusion, the integration of critical thinking into the writing instruction of ESL learners in Uzbekistan is essential for enhancing their writing competency and preparing them for academic success. By fostering analytical skills and encouraging deeper engagement with texts, educators can empower students to express their ideas effectively and confidently. As Uzbekistan continues to position itself within the global educational landscape, prioritizing critical thinking in language education will be crucial for the development of proficient, competent writers.

References:

- 1.Andrews, R. (1995). Teaching and learning argument. London, NY: Cassell.
- 2.Andrews, R. (2000). ‘Introduction: learning to argue in higher education’ in
- 3.Andrews, R and Mitchell, S (eds). Learning to Argue in Higher Education. Portsmouth: Boynton/Cook Publishers, pp. 1-14.
- 4.Ballard, B. and Clanchy, J. (1991). Teaching Students from Overseas: a brief guide for lecturers and supervisors. Melbourne: Longman Cheshire.
- 5.Biggs, J. (1994). ‘What are effective schools? Lessons from East and West’. Australian Educational Researcher, 21/1: 19—39.
- 6.Bonnett, A. (2001). How to Argue: a student’s guide. Harlow: Pearson Education.
- 7.Ramanathan, V. and Kaplan, R. (1996b). ‘Some problematic “channels” in the teaching of critical thinking in current LI composition textbooks: Implications for 12 student-writers’. Issues in Applied Linguistics, 7: 225-249.

8.Scott, M. (2000). Student, critic and literary text: a discussion of 'critical thinking' in a student essay. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 5/3:277-288.

9.Tapper, J. (2004). 'Student perceptions of how critical thinking is embedded in a degree program'. *Higher Education Research and Development*, 23/2: 199-222